

Real-World Diagnostic Patterns and Symptom Progression in Aspirin-Exacerbated Respiratory Disease

Overview

This repository contains statistical analysis outputs generated in R for the manuscript "Real-World Diagnostic Patterns and Symptom Progression in Aspirin-Exacerbated Respiratory Disease". The outputs are organized according to the statistical method used and correspond to the analyses reported in the manuscript (Table 1).

Statistical Analysis

Baseline characteristics were compared across patient groups using one-way ANOVA or the Kruskal–Wallis rank test for continuous variables, depending on data distribution, and the Chi-square test for categorical variables. All statistical analyses were conducted using R software version 4.4.1. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Descriptive Statistics

This section presents descriptive statistics for the study variables included in the analyses. Summary measures are provided to characterize the study population and the main clinical and healthcare utilization variables.

Data Frame Summary

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Valid	Missing
Asthma_age [integer]	Mean (sd) : 46.6 (12.4) min ≤ med ≤ max: 6 ≤ 46 ≤ 74 IQR (CV) : 18 (0.3)	54 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Polyp_age [integer]	Mean (sd) : 48.9 (12.2) min ≤ med ≤ max: 16 ≤ 49 ≤ 81 IQR (CV) : 16 (0.3)	48 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
NSAID_age [integer]	Mean (sd) : 48.1 (12.4) min ≤ med ≤ max: 6 ≤ 48 ≤ 77 IQR (CV) : 15 (0.3)	47 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Valid	Missing
diagnosis_interval_years [integer]	Mean (sd) : 8.3 (4.9) min ≤ med ≤ max: 0 ≤ 8 ≤ 19 IQR (CV) : 8 (0.6)	20 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
CUSTOMER_SEX_CODE [character]	1. F 2. M	101 (55.8%) 80 (44.2%)	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
is_ASTHMA_ANY_expert [integer]	Min : 0 Mean : 0.7 Max : 1	0 : 55 (30.7%) 1 : 124 (69.3%)	179 (98.9%)	2 (1.1%)
doc_visits_total [integer]	Mean (sd) : 416.5 (215.7) min ≤ med ≤ max: 57 ≤ 390 ≤ 1245 IQR (CV) : 259 (0.5)	160 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Valid	Missing
doc_expenses_total [numeric]	Mean (sd) : 32438.3 (16884.9) min ≤ med ≤ max: 3541.3 ≤ 29322 ≤ 96115.7 IQR (CV) : 20111.3 (0.5)	181 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
hospitalizations_count_total [integer]	Mean (sd) : 5.5 (5.2) min ≤ med ≤ max: 1 ≤ 4 ≤ 28 IQR (CV) : 5 (0.9)	23 distinct values	162 (89.5%)	19 (10.5%)
hospitalizations_days_total [integer]	Mean (sd) : 17.8 (37.5) min ≤ med ≤ max: 0 ≤ 6 ≤ 303 IQR (CV) : 15 (2.1)	43 distinct values	162 (89.5%)	19 (10.5%)
visit_ER [integer]	Mean (sd) : 5.8 (5.4) min ≤ med ≤ max: 0 ≤ 4 ≤ 29 IQR (CV) : 6 (0.9)	23 distinct values	171 (94.5%)	10 (5.5%)

Variable	Stats / Values	Freqs (% of Valid)	Valid	Missing
visit_moked_macabbi [integer]	Mean (sd) : 4.5 (3.6) min ≤ med ≤ max: 1 ≤ 4 ≤ 19 IQR (CV) : 4 (0.8)	14 distinct values	96 (53.0%)	85 (47.0%)
SPIROMETRY_count [integer]	Mean (sd) : 7.4 (9.7) min ≤ med ≤ max: 0 ≤ 4 ≤ 65 IQR (CV) : 9 (1.3)	33 distinct values	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)
FESS_count [integer]	Mean (sd) : 0.8 (1.2) min ≤ med ≤ max: 0 ≤ 0 ≤ 6 IQR (CV) : 1 (1.4)	0 : 95 (52.5%) 1 : 49 (27.1%) 2 : 24 (13.3%) 3 : 6 (3.3%) 4 : 4 (2.2%) 5 : 1 (0.6%) 6 : 2 (1.1%)	181 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)

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Chi-Square Test Outputs

This section presents the outputs of Chi-square tests conducted to examine associations between categorical variables and patient groups. For each variable, the corresponding R output is provided.

Sex Distribution Across Diagnostic Sequence Groups

CUSTOMER_SEX_CODE by study_group_mask

<u>CUSTOMER_SEX_CODE</u>	<u>study_group_mask</u>						<u>Total</u>
	123	132	213	231	312	321	
F	31 30.7 %	23 22.8 %	12 11.9 %	10 9.9 %	14 13.9 %	11 10.9 %	101 100 %
M	18 22.5 %	19 23.8 %	21 26.2 %	4 5 %	11 13.8 %	7 8.8 %	80 100 %
Total	49 27.1 %	42 23.2 %	33 18.2 %	14 7.7 %	25 13.8 %	18 9.9 %	181 100 %

$$\chi^2=7.773 \cdot df=5 \cdot \text{Cramer's } V=0.207 \cdot p=0.169$$

Asthma diagnosis by specialist

is_ASTHMA_ANY_expert by study_group_mask

<u>is_ASTHMA_ANY_expert</u>	<u>study_group_mask</u>						<u>Total</u>
	123	132	213	231	312	321	
0	11 20 %	13 23.6 %	9 16.4 %	7 12.7 %	5 9.1 %	10 18.2 %	55 100 %
1	38 30.6 %	27 21.8 %	24 19.4 %	7 5.6 %	20 16.1 %	8 6.5 %	124 100 %
Total	49 27.4 %	40 22.3 %	33 18.4 %	14 7.8 %	25 14 %	18 10.1 %	179 100 %

$$\chi^2=10.829 \cdot df=5 \cdot \text{Cramer's } V=0.246 \cdot \text{Fisher's } p=0.077$$

One-Way ANOVA Outputs

This section presents the outputs of one-way ANOVA analyses conducted to compare continuous variables across patient groups when the assumptions for parametric testing were met. For each variable, the corresponding R output is provided.

Age of asthma onset

```
>
> AOV1 <- aov(mydata_ALL$Asthma_age ~ mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
> summary(AOV1)
```

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	
mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask	5	2766	553.2	
Residuals	175	25007	142.9	
		F value	Pr(>F)	
mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask		3.871	0.00237	**
Residuals				

```
---
Signif. codes:
0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
> describe.by(mydata_ALL$Asthma_age, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Descriptive statistics by group

```
group: 123
  vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 49 46.04 12.06 46 46.24 14.83 21 72
  range skew kurtosis se
x1 51 -0.07 -0.85 1.72
```

```
-----
group: 132
  vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 42 42.45 10.42 43 42.62 11.86 19 63
  range skew kurtosis se
x1 44 -0.11 -0.75 1.61
```

```
-----
group: 213
  vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 33 46 13.52 45 45.93 17.79 22 70
  range skew kurtosis se
x1 48 0.08 -1.12 2.35
```

```
-----
group: 231
  vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 14 51.07 12.46 51.5 51.83 11.12 24 69
  range skew kurtosis se
x1 45 -0.45 -0.61 3.33
-----
```

```

group: 312
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 25 45.92 13.76    46  46.33 11.86   6  74
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    68 -0.45    1.05 2.75
-----

```

```

group: 321
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 18 56.39  8.28    56  56.5 11.86  43  68
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    25 -0.27   -1.27 1.95

```

Age of nasal polyp onset

```

>
> AOV1 <- aov(mydata_ALL$Polyp_age ~ mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
> summary(AOV1)

```

```

              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask  5   2299   459.7
Residuals                   175  24688  141.1
              F value Pr(>F)
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask  3.259 0.00772 **
Residuals
---

```

Signif. codes:

```

0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

> describe.by(mydata_ALL$Polyp_age, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)

```

Descriptive statistics by group

```

group: 123
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 49 49.02 11.54    49  48.95 11.86  26  75
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    49 0.08   -0.62 1.65
-----

```

```

group: 132
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 42 52.14 11.32    51.5  52.71  8.9  23  72
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    49 -0.33   -0.18 1.75
-----

```

```

group: 213
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 33 43.21 12.52    44  43.19 16.31  22  65
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    43  0   -1.06 2.18
-----

```

```

group: 231
  vars n mean    sd median trimmed  mad min max
x1    1 14 43.36 13.13    43  43.25 14.83  23  65
  range skew kurtosis  se
x1    42 0.21   -1.27 3.51

```

```
-----
group: 312
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 25 51.48 12.95    49  51.48 8.9 16 81
  range skew kurtosis se
X1    65 -0.17    0.81 2.59
-----
```

```
group: 321
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 18 52.17 10.18    52  52.44 10.38 34 66
  range skew kurtosis se
X1    32 -0.38   -1.03 2.4
```

Age of NSAID sensitivity onset

```
>
>
> AOV1 <- aov(mydata_ALL$NSAID_age ~ mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
> summary(AOV1)
```

```
              Df Sum Sq Mean Sq
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask  5   2423   484.5
Residuals                   175  25192   144.0
              F value Pr(>F)
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask  3.366 0.00628 **
Residuals
```

```
---
Signif. codes:
0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
> describe.by(mydata_ALL$NSAID_age, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Descriptive statistics by group

```
group: 123
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 49 52.55 11.63    52  52.37 14.83 28 77
  range skew kurtosis se
X1    49 0.11   -0.94 1.66
-----
```

```
group: 132
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 42 45.52 10.42   45.5  45.85 11.12 23 64
  range skew kurtosis se
X1    41 -0.27   -0.73 1.61
-----
```

```
group: 213
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 33 50.91 13.43    51  50.96 14.83 24 75
  range skew kurtosis se
X1    51 -0.03   -0.88 2.34
-----
```

```
group: 231
  vars n mean   sd median trimmed mad min max
X1    1 14 45.71 12.68   47.5  45.83 14.83 24 66
```

```
range skew kurtosis se
x1 42 0.07 -1.16 3.39
```

group: 312

```
vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 25 42.64 12.94 43 43 11.86 6 70
```

```
range skew kurtosis se
x1 64 -0.4 0.91 2.59
```

group: 321

```
vars n mean sd median trimmed mad min max
x1 1 18 45.89 11.8 48 46.06 11.12 24 65
```

```
range skew kurtosis se
x1 41 -0.41 -1.09 2.78
```

Kruskal-Wallis Test Outputs

This section presents the outputs of Kruskal–Wallis rank-sum tests conducted to compare continuous variables across patient groups when the assumptions for parametric testing were not met. For each variable, the corresponding R output is provided.

Diagnosis Interval

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$diagnosis_interval_years, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

```
kruskal-wallis rank sum test
```

```
data: mydata_ALL$diagnosis_interval_years and mydata_ALL$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 13.255, df = 5,
p-value = 0.0211
```

```
>
```

```
> summary_all_diagnosis_interval_years <- summarize_all(diagnosis_interval_years)
```

```
> summary_all_diagnosis_interval_years
```

```
  median Q1 Q3    mean    SE
1      8  4 12  8.276243 0.3673352
```

```
>
```

```
> summary_by_group_diagnosis_interval_years <- summarize_by_variable(diagnosis_interval_years)
```

```
> summary_by_group_diagnosis_interval_years
```

```
# A tibble: 6 × 6
```

```
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3    mean    SE
  <chr>              <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                 6     4     9     6.51 0.613
2 132                 9    5.25 14.5    9.69 0.856
3 213                 8     4    10     7.70 0.764
4 231                 6.5  4    11.8    7.71 1.37
5 312                 9     5    11     8.84 0.941
6 321                11    8.25 13     10.5  1.16
```

```
>
```

Number of physician visits

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$doc_visits_total, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

```
kruskal-wallis rank sum test
```

```
data: mydata_ALL$doc_visits_total and mydata_ALL$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 3.03, df = 5, p-value
= 0.6954
```

```

> summary_all_doc_visits_total <- summarize_all(doc_visits_total)
> summary_all_doc_visits_total
  median  Q1  Q3    mean    SE
1    390 264 523 416.4696 16.03207
>
> summary_by_group_doc_visits_total <-
summarize_by_variable(doc_visits_total)
> summary_by_group_doc_visits_total
# A tibble: 6 × 6
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                413  244  568  436.  33.0
2 132                320  254. 498.  395.  31.2
3 213                354  215  474  372.  32.7
4 231                365  305. 588.  483.  80.3
5 312                433  292  490  422.  34.8
6 321                417  300. 516.  436.  55.2
>

```

Total costs of physician visits

```

> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$doc_expenses_total, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)

```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$doc_expenses_total and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 3.5072, df = 5,
p-value = 0.6223

```

> summary_all_doc_expenses_total <- summarize_all(doc_expenses_total)
> summary_all_doc_expenses_total
  median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
1 29322.02 20584.19 40695.44 32438.35 1255.042
>
> summary_by_group_doc_expenses_total <-
summarize_by_variable(doc_expenses_total)
> summary_by_group_doc_expenses_total
# A tibble: 6 × 6
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                30094. 19047. 44999. 33369. 2493.
2 132                25436. 19081. 39830. 30858. 2531.
3 213                28594. 17725. 38764. 29047. 2700.
4 231                28044. 23229. 43181. 37629. 6378.
5 312                33666. 23014. 39020. 33093. 2573.
6 321                32557. 23108. 41179. 34864. 4269.
>

```

Number of hospitalizations

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$hospitalizations_count_total,  
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$hospitalizations_count_total and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 5.0593, df = 5,
p-value = 0.4087

```
> summary_all_hospitalizations_count_total <-  
summarize_all(hospitalizations_count_total)  
> summary_all_hospitalizations_count_total  
  median Q1 Q3   mean   SE  
1     4  2  7 5.524691 0.4052982  
>  
> summary_by_group_hospitalizations_count_total <-  
summarize_by_variable(hospitalizations_count_total)  
> summary_by_group_hospitalizations_count_total  
# A tibble: 6 × 6  
  study_group_mask median   Q1   Q3  mean   SE  
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>  
1 123                4     3   8     5.98 0.704  
2 132                4     2   6     4.5  0.637  
3 213                5     2   9     6.97 1.25  
4 231                5     2  5.25  6.33 2.13  
5 312                3     2  6.25  4.79 0.963  
6 321                3     2   6     4    0.707
```

Number of hospitalizations days

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$hospitalizations_days_total,  
mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$hospitalizations_days_total and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 3.2546, df = 5,
p-value = 0.6608

```
> summary_all_hospitalizations_days_total <-  
summarize_all(hospitalizations_days_total)  
> summary_all_hospitalizations_days_total  
  median Q1 Q3   mean   SE  
1     6  2 17 17.83333 2.943403  
>  
> summary_by_group_hospitalizations_days_total <-  
summarize_by_variable(hospitalizations_days_total)  
> summary_by_group_hospitalizations_days_total  
# A tibble: 6 × 6
```

	study_group_mask	median	Q1	Q3	mean	SE
	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>
1	123	8	1.5	16	17.0	4.07
2	132	5	2	13	16.1	7.36
3	213	6	4	22.8	17.0	3.95
4	231	10	2	27.8	41.5	24.7
5	312	3.5	2	11.8	15	5.77
6	321	11	1	17	11.2	2.99

Number of ER visits

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$visit_ER, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$visit_ER and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
 Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 2.778, df = 5, p-value
 = 0.7342

```
> summary_all_visit_ER <- summarize_all(visit_ER)
> summary_all_visit_ER
  median Q1 Q3    mean      SE
1     4  2  8 5.766082 0.4154168
>
> summary_by_group_visit_ER <- summarize_by_variable(visit_ER)
> summary_by_group_visit_ER
# A tibble: 6 × 6
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                4     3     8   6.09 0.743
2 132                4     3     7.5 5.51 0.648
3 213                3   1.75  7.5 6.38 1.36
4 231                6     1     8   7.15 1.94
5 312                3     2     6   4.96 1.01
6 321                4     2     6   4.38 0.706
```

Number of MHS emergency department visits

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$visit_moked_macabbi, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

Kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$visit_moked_macabbi and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
 Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 8.1083, df = 5,
 p-value = 0.1504

```
> summary_all_visit_moked_macabbi <- summarize_all(visit_moked_macabbi)
> summary_all_visit_moked_macabbi
```

```

  median Q1 Q3      mean      SE
1      4  2  6 4.541667 0.3710809
>
> summary_by_group_visit_moked_macabbi <-
summarize_by_variable(visit_moked_macabbi)
> summary_by_group_visit_moked_macabbi
# A tibble: 6 × 6
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                3     1.5    7  4.93 0.854
2 132                4     2.5    6  4.78 0.635
3 213                3     2      5  4.18 1.06
4 231                6.5   3.75   7  5.62 0.706
5 312                3.5   2      5  4.36 0.868
6 321                2     1      3  2.29 0.606

```

Number of spirometry procedures

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$SPIROMETRY_count, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

kruskal-wallis rank sum test

data: mydata_ALL\$SPIROMETRY_count and mydata_ALL\$study_group_mask
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 1.7019, df = 5,
p-value = 0.8887

```
> summary_all_SPIROMETRY_count <- summarize_all(SPIROMETRY_count)
> summary_all_SPIROMETRY_count
```

```

  median Q1 Q3      mean      SE
1      4  1 10 7.414365 0.7187723
>
> summary_by_group_SPIROMETRY_count <- summarize_by_variable(SPIROMETRY_count)
> summary_by_group_SPIROMETRY_count
# A tibble: 6 × 6
  study_group_mask median    Q1    Q3  mean    SE
  <chr>             <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
1 123                4     3     11  9.04 1.75
2 132                4.5   0.25 10.5  6.17 1.09
3 213                3     0     10  8.15 1.91
4 231                3     1.25  9.75  7.79 3.27
5 312                4     2     9   6.12 1.13
6 321                4     1.25  8.25  6.06 1.58

```

Number of FESS procedures

```
> kruskal.test(mydata_ALL$FESS_count, mydata_ALL$study_group_mask)
```

```
    Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test
```

```
data: mydata_ALL$FESS_count and mydata_ALL$study_group_mask
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 12.361, df = 5,
p-value = 0.03016
```

```
> summary_all_FESS_count <- summarize_all(FESS_count)
```

```
> summary_all_FESS_count
```

```
  median Q1 Q3      mean      SE
1      0  0  1 0.8176796 0.08564625
```

```
>
```

```
> summary_by_group_FESS_count <- summarize_by_variable(FESS_count)
```

```
> summary_by_group_FESS_count
```

```
# A tibble: 6 × 6
```

	study_group_mask	median	Q1	Q3	mean	SE
	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>
1	123	1	0	2	1	0.177
2	132	0	0	1	0.619	0.148
3	213	1	0	2	1.30	0.287
4	231	0	0	0	0.143	0.0971
5	312	1	0	1	0.76	0.156
6	321	0.5	0	1	0.5	0.121